

11-16 AUGUST 2019

22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Carbon Quantum Dots Using Polyphenol Compounds :Skin Anti-Aging

Seok Won Park

School of Biomedical Engineering, Inje University

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Characteristic of Carbon Quantum Dots

Morphology

Fluorescence

Surface Functionalization

Crystallinity

Anti-aging property of Carbon Quantum Dots

**Free radical
Scavenging activity**

**Collagenase
Inhibition activity**

**Elastase
Inhibition activity**

**Tyrosinase
Inhibition activity**